

MODIFICATION OF PLA-BASED BIO-NANOCOMPOSITE WITH NCC

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Abstract: *In this article, the properties of bio-nanocomposite with poly(lactic acid) (PLA)/polycarbonate (PC) blend, prepared with reactive extrusion, are described. For good dispersion of nanocrystalline cellulose (NCC) mixture of two compatibilizers was used, without surface treatment of NCC. To enhance the miscibility of the bio-nanocomposite two compounding cycles were performed. To enable the crystallization during the cooling of PLA, CaCO₃ was added in all series. A mixture of PLA/PC with all additives and without NCC was used as a reference. The addition of NCC enhanced stiffness, strength, and elongation at break, showing good interfacial interaction between thermoplastic matrix and NCC due to proper compatibilizer mixtures. At lower NCC loading the mechanical properties were enhanced also beyond the glass transition temperature. The crystal moieties formation was characterized by Flash DSC. At 1 % and 2 wt.% NCC loading the time for crystal formation is min. 600 s, at 5 wt.% NCC loading time is min. 100 s. The toughness was enhanced except for the sample with 5 wt.% NCC and second compounding cycle due to the PLA and NCC degradation. With the material, the design jars were produced. Production was possible due to the material modification, with plain PLA production via injection molding not possible due to the negative angle. Modified bio-nanocomposite is suitable for the production of design injection molded parts.*

Keywords: PLA, bio-nanocomposite, compatibilizer, reactive extrusion

1 INTRODUCTION

Biopolymers, biopolymer blends and biocomposites are becoming more and more interesting for research and industry because they pollute the environment

less. Researchers are working hard to avoid the disadvantages of biopolymers. Environmentally friendly materials, especially biodegradable ones such as PLA, poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) (PHB), poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL), poly(butylene succinate) (PBA) and PBAT, are attracting great interest from researchers and industry (Ma, 2011). The properties of PLA together with its ability to be processed on conventional equipment make it possible to replace conventional petroleum-based thermoplastics (Zeng, Li and Du, 2015; Murariu and Dubois, 2016). There are numerous research efforts in the field of reactive modification of biopolymers using various reactive agents such as organic peroxides and multifunctional crosslinking modifying agents (Dluzneski, 2001; Tolinski, 2009; Kruželák, Sýkora and Hudec, 2017). Researchers reported the degradation of PLA in combination with crosslinking by modifying PLA with peroxides (Takamura *et al.*, 2008, 2010; Rytlewski, Zenkiewicz and Malinowski, 2011; Signori *et al.*, 2015). Reactive compatibilisation is a very cost-effective processing technology, an environmentally friendly process as it does not contain solvents, does not require special equipment and can be easily converted to industrial production (Formela *et al.*, 2018). In microcellulose and nanocellulose, the cellulose surface is chemically modified to improve the surface interaction of the cellulose with the polymer matrix, usually by esterification and silanisation or by plasma and corona surface treatment, which is also required in the case of PLA matrix (Singha *et al.*, 2019). Unmodified bacterial cellulose nanomatrices were incorporated into the PLA matrix by electrospinning, followed by incorporation of the nanostructured fibres into the PLA matrix by melt blending. The stiffness and strength were increased while the ductility remained at the level of pure PLA (Martínez-Sanz, Lopez-Rubio and Lagaron, 2012). Major research efforts have been made to improve the reactive compatibility of PLA, including petroleum-based polymers. Chain extenders have been used for the PLA/PC blend to increase toughness (Zhao *et al.*, 2020). A stiffer PLA base blend was mixed with PC, a hydrogenated styrene-butadiene-styrene block copolymer and a reactive compatibiliser, poly(ethylene-co-glycidyl methacrylate). Thermal stability and excellent toughness were achieved (Hashima, Nishitsuji and Inoue, 2010).

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Sample

Commercially available PLA with the trade name Ingeo 4043D was provided by Plastika Trček, Slovenia. Commercially available polycarbonate with the trade name Lexan 243 R was obtained from Sabic, Austria. NCC was donated by the company Navitas, Slovenia. Commercially available SEBS-g-MA with the trade name FG 1901 GT was purchased from Kraton, Germany. Commercially available

TPU copolymer with the trade name Kuramiron U TU -S5265 was purchased from Kuraray, Germany. Commercially available CaCO₃ with the trade name Calplex Extra was donated by Calcit, Slovenia. Reactive compounding was performed twice. The composition of the samples is listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition of the samples of the third series and number of compounding cycles.

<i>Sample</i>	<i>PLA (wt.%)</i>	<i>PC (wt.%)</i>	<i>SEBS (wt.%)</i>	<i>TPU (wt.%)</i>	<i>CaCO₃ (wt.%)</i>	<i>NCC (wt.%)</i>	<i>Compounding cycles</i>
<i>PLAPC</i>	42	40	10	5	3	0	1
<i>PLAPC 1NCC-1</i>	41	40	10	5	3	1	1
<i>PLAPC 1NCC-2</i>	41	40	10	5	3	1	2
<i>PLAPC 2NCC-1</i>	40	40	10	5	3	2	1
<i>PLAPC 2NCC-2</i>	40	40	10	5	3	2	2
<i>PLAPC 5NCC-1</i>	37	40	10	5	3	5	1
<i>PLAPC 5NCC-2</i>	37	40	10	5	3	5	2

2. 2 Reactive compounding

For the first reactive extrusion cycle, the materials were mixed separately and extruded on the Labtech LTE 20-44 twin screw extruder. The screw diameter was 20 mm, the L/D ratio was 44:1 and the screw speed was 600 rpm. The temperature profile for the PLAPC samples increased from the hopper (165°C) to the die (200°C). Vacuum extraction was performed during reactive extrusion to remove the volatile gaseous products of reactive extrusion. The vacuum was set to 50 mbar. After compounding, the two produced filaments with a diameter of 3 mm were cooled in a water bath and formed into pellets with a length of about 5 mm and a diameter of 3 mm. In the second reactive extrusion cycles, the produced pellets of bio-nanocomposites were extruded on the same extruder with identical extruder settings.

2. 3 Injection moulding

The injection moulding was carried out on a Krauss Maffei 50-180 CX injection moulding machine with a screw diameter of 30 mm and a clamping force of 500 kN. The cold runner mould was used to produce the samples. The mould had two cavities, one with a dumbbell-shaped mould of type 1BA (ISO 527-1), the second with a cuboid-shaped mould (ISO 178/ ISO 179). The temperature was increased from the hopper (185°C) to the die (200°C), the injection speed was set to 60 mm/min and the mould temperature to 30°C, and the cooling time was set to 10 s. The mould was then cooled down to a temperature of 10°C. During plasticising, the back pressure was set to 150 bar and the screw speed to 50 rpm. The low screw speed was used to prevent thermal degradation of the bio-nanocomposite

melt and to minimise shear during processing due to the higher processing temperature.

2. 4 Methods for characteriaztion of the bio-nanocomposites

The tensile tests were carried out with the Shimadzu AG -X plus according to ISO 527-1. Five measurements were taken for each sample. In the tensile tests, tensile stiffness (E_t), tensile strength (σ_m), tensile yield strain (ϵ_m) and elongation at break (ϵ_{tb}) were determined. The thermomechanical properties were investigated using a Perkin Elmer DMA 8000 dynamic mechanical analyser. The viscoelastic properties of the samples were analysed by recording the storage modulus (E') and loss factor ($\tan \delta$) as a function of temperature. The viscoelastic analyses were performed on samples with dimensions of approximately 42 x 5 x 2 mm. The samples were heated at 2°C/min from room temperature (23°C) to 180°C in an air atmosphere. A frequency of 1 Hz and an amplitude of 20 μm were used in dual- cantilever mode. Thermal measurements were performed with a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC 2, Mettler Toledo) under a nitrogen atmosphere (20 mL/min). The temperature of the samples was raised from 0 to 200°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min and held in the molten state for 5 minutes to quench the thermal history. After cooling at 10°C/min, the samples were reheated to 200°C at 10°C/min. The crystallisation temperature (T_c), crystallisation enthalpy (ΔH_c), glass transition temperature (T_g), cold crystallisation temperature (T_{cc}), cold crystallisation enthalpy (ΔH_{cc}), melting temperature (T_m) and melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) were determined from the cooling scan and the second heating scan. The crystallisation behaviour of the samples was determined using the Mettler Toledo Flash DSC 1 with Huber intercooler TC45 and nitrogen purge gas (50 ml/min). Samples were cooled from melt (200°C) to the desired temperature, rapidly heated to the ageing temperature (90°C for 100 s), rapidly cooled to 15°C, reheated to 120°C and then cold crystallised at 120°C for various times (from 0.1 s to 2,400 s). All cooling and heating segments were rapidly cooled and heated (500°C/s) to prevent crystallisation during cooling and heating. The first heating run was from 15°C to 200°C. For the evaluation of the heating section, segment No. 12 was taken and the melting temperature and melting enthalpy were characterised. The mass of the samples was determined from the normalised change in specific heat capacity at the glass transition based on the evaluation of the DSC 2 measurements.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical properties

The results of the tensile strength are shown in Table 2. Compared to the reference, the mixtures with the addition of 1 % NCC showed higher stiffness, strength, and elongation at break. Further addition of NCC increases the tensile stiffness at the first mixing cycle but decreases the strength and elongation at break. The addition of 5% NCC reduces stiffness, strength, and elongation. An additional mixing cycle with the addition of 1 % NCC increases tensile stiffness and strength and maintains elongation at break. An additional mixing cycle with 2 % NCC addition reduces tensile stiffness while maintaining tensile strength and elongation at break. An additional mixing cycle with 5 % NCC additive reduces the stiffness, strength, and elongation. It can be concluded that the mixing conditions of the reaction ensure a good interfacial interaction between the thermoplastic matrix and the NCC and ensure a good dispersion of the NCC in the thermoplastic matrix at NCC concentrations below 5 %. The comparison of the first and second reaction mixture suggests that with an additional cycle of the reaction mixture with the addition of 2 % and 5 % NCC, the degradation of PLA and possibly also of NCC is already taking place. This is evidenced by the decrease in tensile strength and elongation, which in the case of the PLAPC matrix is a good indicator of the onset of degradation of the PLA matrix, and the lower stiffness is an indicator of the onset of degradation of the NCC. The reaction mixing of PLA and PC in the presence of a combination of two compatibilisers and a filler provides good mixing of PLA and PC while ensuring good interfacial interactions and dispersion of NCC in the thermoplastic matrix at NCC concentrations below 2%.

Table 2. Summarized results from the tensile tests.

Sample	Tensile test results		
	E_t (GPa)	σ_m (MPa)	ϵ_{tb} (%)
PLAPC	2.17 ± 0.16	31.6 ± 0.3	4.8 ± 0.6
PLAPC 1NCC-1	2.37 ± 0.31	40.5 ± 0.2	9.6 ± 0.4
PLAPC 1NCC-2	2.44 ± 0.24	40.7 ± 0.4	9.5 ± 0.8
PLAPC 2NCC-1	2.38 ± 0.27	37.4 ± 0.2	8.7 ± 0.9
PLAPC 2NCC-2	2.33 ± 0.11	37.3 ± 0.4	8.8 ± 1.0
PLAPC 5NCC-1	2.23 ± 0.07	36.6 ± 0.5	8.6 ± 0.6
PLAPC 5NCC-2	2.01 ± 0.13	31.5 ± 0.6	4.6 ± 0.3

3.2 Thermo-mechanical properties

The storage modulus curves (Figures 1 and 2) show the first drop in glass transition temperature for PLA. The storage modulus is higher in this range (75°C

to 100°C) with higher NCC content. Above 100°C, the storage modulus increases due to cold crystallisation of the material. The lowest temperature peak during cold crystallisation was observed in the PLAPC sample (114°C) and the highest peak in the PLAPC 1NCC-2 sample (119°C). The addition of NCC to PLA-based compounds inhibits the cold crystallisation of PLA. At low NCC loading (1 wt%), NCC acts as a reinforcement for the PLA-based compound; at higher loadings (2 wt% and 5 wt%), the stiffness of the nanocomposites drops below that of the neat matrix. The dissipation factor curve shows two sharp peaks at 69°C and 160°C (Figures 1 and 2) for the PLA and PC matrices. The height of the first peak is lowest for the PLAPC 1NCC sample and highest for the PLAPC sample. The height of the second peak is lowest for the PLAPC sample and highest for the PLAPC 1NCC sample. In the second mixing cycle, the peak heights are higher, indicating the start of matrix degradation. The PLAPC 1NCC sample shows the most elastic behaviour after the first mixing cycle. The good surface interaction of the NCC with the matrix due to the compatibiliser in the PLAPC 1NCC sample increases the storage modulus, keeps the storage modulus at a high level and reduces the peak height of the loss factor for PLA. The higher peak loss factor for the PC sample is due to the highest cold crystallisation temperature for the PLAPC 1NCC sample and thus the overlap between the glass transition temperature of PC and the onset of melting of PLA. The DMA results show that reactive extrusion is a suitable technology for processing bio-nanocomposites even without surface modification of the natural fibres.

Figure 1. Summarized results of storage modulus (left) and loss factor (right) for the first compounding cycle.

Figure 2. Summarized results of storage modulus (left) and loss factor (right) for the second compounding cycle.

3. 3 Thermal properties

The results of the DSC evaluation are shown in Table 3. During the first mixing cycle, the cold crystallisation temperature, melting temperature and crystallinity were increased for all bio-nanocomposite samples compared to the PLAPC reference. During the second mixing cycle, the cold crystallisation temperatures decreased and the crystallinity increased. The higher crystallinity indicates a good homogeneity of the bio-nanocomposites.

Table 3. Summarized results from the 2nd heating from DSC tests.

Sample	T_g (°C)	ΔC_p (J/gK)	T_{cc} (°C)	ΔH_{cc} (J/g)	T_m (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)	Diff. ΔH_m (J/g)
PLAPC	59.8	0.11	123.6	5.35	152.0	5.37	0.02
PLAPC 1NCC-1	60.8	0.09	133.3	0.32	152.2	0.37	0.05
PLAPC 1NCC-2	60.6	0.09	128.3	0.04	152.2	0.33	0.29
PLAPC 2NCC-1	61.1	0.08	133.4	0.13	152.4	0.31	0.18
PLAPC 2NCC-2	60.7	0.09	131.6	0.18	152.8	0.52	0.34
PLAPC 5NCC-1	61.1	0.06	130.4	0.24	153.2	0.48	0.24
PLAPC 5NCC-2	60.1	0.08	128.4	1.28	152.9	1.67	0.39

The kinetics of crystallisation were characterised by Flash DSC (Figure 3). The onset of formation of crystal units was at 90°C for 100 s after ageing and at 120°C for 100 s after ageing for all samples. A shorter time is not sufficient for the formation of crystalline units. The higher NCC loading promoted the formation of crystalline units as did the second mixing cycle. The fastest and largest increase in crystalline segments was observed in the PLAPC 5NCC-2 sample up to a cold crystallisation time of 600 s and thereafter in the PLAPC 1NCC-2 sample. It can be concluded that NCC inhibits cold crystallisation at shorter times and increases cold crystallisation at longer times at elevated temperatures. The mobility of PLA chains at elevated temperatures reaches the threshold for the formation of crystalline units after 600 s at NCC loading of 1 wt% and 2 wt%. At an NCC loading of 5 wt%, 100 s is sufficient due to the higher amount of NCC particles in the

matrix. The results also indicate that NCC agglomeration occurs to a lesser extent and increases with increasing NCC content.

Figure 3. Summarized results of crystallization enthalpy (left) and melting temperature (right) of the samples after aging at 90°C for 100 s and various cold crystallization times at 120°C.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The evaluation of the mechanical properties showed that new properties were obtained by the addition of NCC. The mixture was able to achieve high temperature stability due to the addition of PC. The produced bio-nanocomposites showed good miscibility of PLA and PC and good surface interaction between the thermoplastic matrix and the natural fibres, although the surface of the natural fibres was not changed. Furthermore, the DSC results showed an altered morphological behaviour of the PLAPC 1NCC-2 bionanocomposite. Longer residence time at elevated temperature accelerates crystallisation as a result of degradation of PLA and NCC due to shorter PLA chains and smaller NCC particles, which serve as nuclei for the initiation of heterogeneous PLA crystallisation. At the same time, it can be observed that NCC is well distributed in the thermoplastic matrix due to the increasing crystallinity. Good surface interaction between the thermoplastic matrix and narurium fibres was achieved by suitable compatibilisers and loading. The suitability of the reaction mixture was evaluated by the simultaneous increase in stiffness and elongation at break in tensile test, change in storage modulus and loss factor in DMA, change in cold crystallisation temperature and crystallinity in DSC. The produced bio-nanocomposites showed a stiffer behaviour with high stiffness and strength at the same time. The addition of NCC also affected the morphology of the bio-nanocomposites, which can be controlled by the processing parameters. A second cycle of reactive mixing at 1% NCC loading showed that recycling of the new bio-nanocomposites can be performed without significant effects on the properties of the recycled products. The present work shows that existing polymer processing equipment is suitable for the production of bio-

nanocomposites and their recycling. To characterise the dependence on the amount of added NCC in bio(nano)composites, further studies should investigate the addition of less than 1 wt% NCC to PLA-based bio(nano)composite blends.

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